

Assessment of the sandy dunes and shoreline dynamics at Sonadia Island

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INSTITUTE OF FORESTRY AND ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES

UNIVERSITY OF CHITTAGONG

CHITTAGONG-4331

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This dissertation has been submitted as partial fulfillment for the one-year professional degree of Masters of Science in Forestry (Thesis)

Supervised by: Dr. Mohammad Mosharraf Hossain Professor, Institute of forestry and environmental sciences, University of Chittagong (IFESCU). Chittagong-4331	Submitted by: Yaqub Ali Examination Roll: 16208022 Registration No: 16208022 IFESCU Chittagong-4331, Bangladesh
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INSTITUTE OF FORESTRY AND ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES

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CHITTAGONG-4331

CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that Yaqub Ali, Examination Roll No.16208022, Registration No.16208022, and Session: 2019-2020 has prepared this thesis dissertation entitled- **Assessment of the sandy dunes and shoreline dynamics at Sonadia Island** - under my supervision. I do hereby approve the style and content of this dissertation. This dissertation has been prepared as a requirement for the partial fulfillment of the one-year degree of Masters of Science in Forestry (Thesis) from the Institute of Forestry and Environmental Sciences, University of Chittagong, Bangladesh.

.....

Dr. Mohammad Mosharraf Hossain

Professor,
Institute of Forestry and Environmental Sciences
University of Chittagong,
Chittagong-4331, Bangladesh.

DECLARATION

This dissertation entitled- **Assessment of the sandy dunes and shoreline dynamics at Sonadia Island** - has been prepared as a requirement for the partial fulfillment of the degree of one-year degree Masters of Science in Forestry (Thesis) under the supervision of Dr. Mohammad Mosharraf Hossain, professor, Institute of Forestry and Environmental Sciences, University of Chittagong. The work has not previously been accepted in substance for a degree nor has it been submitted in any previous application for any degree. I do hereby declare that this dissertation is the result of my original work, except where otherwise stated. Other sources are acknowledged by explicit references to the authors. This dissertation will be available for photocopying, seminar, and library use, and the summary to be available to outside organizations.

.....

Yaqub Ali

Examination Roll No: 16208022

Registration No: 16208022

Session: 2019-20

Institute of Forestry and Environmental Sciences

University of Chittagong.

Chittagong4331, Bangladesh.

**Dedicated to
My Beloved Departed Father**

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Author

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Abstract

The coastal ecosystem is one of the most dynamic ecosystems in nature, due to anthropogenic and natural causes it changes morphologically and physically. The present study includes a comprehensive analysis of the coastal dynamics at Sonadia Island in Bangladesh. The study utilized a range of methodologies, including field surveys, satellite imagery analysis, statistical techniques, and projection modeling to examine half a century of coastal change and the impact of different factors like sea level rise (SLR), tropical cyclones, and coastal vegetation, sandy dunes and dunes elevation on it. Ten coastal profiles with 1.5-2km intervals and 307 transects with an interval of 50m across the beach, 9 shorelines along the beach for 1972, 1979, 1989, 1991, 1996, 1999, 2005, 2014, and 2023 were used for this analysis using Google Earth Engine (GEE), Esri ArcGIS, and USGS Digital Shoreline Analysis System (DSAS) tools. The examination of Linear Regression Rate (LRR), Endpoint Rate (EPR), and Weighted LRR (WLR) indicates that cyclones in 1991 and 1997 accelerated coastal erosion, while plantation activities from 2003 to 2015 resulted in significant accretion in previously eroding areas. The present investigation discloses an overall erosion rate of 0.93m/yr. at EPR and 1.9m/yr. at LRR from 1972 to 2023 on the Island. Considering LRR, SLR alone accounts for 13.77-21.58% of the overall erosion, and when considering EPR, SLR contributes to 28.28-40.09% of erosion on the Island over the past five decades. Furthermore, a predictive model using Kalman Filter projected shoreline positions in 2034 and 2044, suggesting that accretion would occur predominantly in the northern and middle sections, while the southern region remained at risk of erosion. The examination of the coastal profile across 10 transects at Sonadia revealed that the quantity and elevation of sandy dunes play a significant role ($P < 0.05$) in mitigating coastal erosion. Nevertheless, the width of the coastal vegetation belt was found to have an insignificant impact ($P > 0.05$) on both the numbers and elevation of the dunes. The research findings of coastal dynamics on Sonadia offer invaluable insights for effective coastal ecosystem management, mitigating the profound and dynamic changes driven by both natural and human-induced factors and safeguarding these dynamic environments by taking necessary steps before taking future national projects at Sonadia Island.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the research

Around 10% of the global population lives along coastal areas less than 10m height above mean sea level (MSL) (Athanasίου et al., 2019; McGranahan et al., 2007) and this percentage is expected to increase due to the continuous high rate of population growth (Athanasίου et al., 2019). The world beach environment is continuously degraded and the threat of degradation increases due to the increasing trend of human activities in the coastal area in the 21st century (Brown & McLachlan, 2002; Schlacher et al., 2006, 2008). Global climate change and sea level raise further accelerate the coastal retreat (Feagin et al., 2005; Harley et al., 2006). Coastal erosion is a significant and global issue (Biswas & Islam, 2017), and Bangladesh is not out of that. Coastal erosion is a considerable phenomenon in Bangladesh (Islam et al., 2020; Salauddin et al., 2018) as this area is directly exposed to natural disasters like cyclones, tornadoes, storm surges, flooding, river bank, coastal erosion and so on (Ali, 1996; Islam et al., 2020) due to its geographical location and geomorphic conditions of this country (Ali, 1996; Choudhury, 1989; Haider et al., 1991; Islam et al., 2020).

Coastal dunes are natural formations formed through the aggregation of sand by the trapping of the aeolian that moves sand behind obstacles like macrophyte wrack and pioneer vegetation (Anonymous, 2023; Cornish, 1897; Lü et al., 2018; Martínez & Psuty, 2004). A diverse community of organisms like bacteria, nematodes, yeasts, fungi, mites, macrofauna and pioneer vegetation directly or indirectly participate during the natural formation of dunes (Marshall & Banks, 2013; Speed, 2005). Dunes with higher elevation form through the trapping of sand behinds the pioneer and early-stage vegetation (Marshall & Banks, 2013).

A wide range of human activities including housing and recreation, agriculture, industrial and commercial activities, military activities, disposal of waste, and mining activities degrade coastal dunes (Lithgow et al., 2013; Nordstrom, 2021). Such degradations lead to gradual and unsustainable alteration in the coastal process threatening the biodiversity and endemic species (Ayyad, 2003; De Luca et al., 2011; Faggi & Dadon, 2011; Lithgow et al., 2013; Martinez et al., 2006; Nordstrom, 2021; Waikato, 2006). Besides the anthropogenic actors, some natural actors

like cyclones, strong winds, and floods cause back sweep of the coastal deposits and dunes – flattening the beach profile and leading to a negative sediment budget (Botero et al., 2017; Marshall & Banks, 2013; Portz, 2008).

The coastal environment and the dunes system provide aesthetic beauty for tourism and generate economic benefits from birds, fishes, turtles, crabs, oysters, etc., in addition to other services like protection from cyclones by acting as transitional zones between the coastal and urban structures (Botero et al., 2017; Schlacher et al., 2008). Thus the management of the coastal environment is critical for the conservation of the unique coastal features and the sustainability of this unique environment (Schlacher et al., 2008). Restoration and preservation of this continuously degrading environment become inevitable to reduce the further loss and degradation of coastal and beach ecosystems from haphazard human activities (Lithgow et al., 2013).

Bangladesh is a low-lying deltaic country with having very unstable coastline with the highest level of vulnerability due to climate change, sea level rise (SLR), and tropical cyclones (Salman et al., 2018). These deltas receive tremendous sediment flow from the upland of the Ganges, Brahmaputra, and Meghna river basins (Crawford et al., 2021). The coastline of Bangladesh is about 710km long with a variety of ecological and economic features like mangrove forests, tidal flat, islands, estuaries, peninsula, rural and urban settlements areas, industrial areas, and ports (Ahmad, 2019; Hossain, 2001; Iftekhar, 2006). The coastal area can be categorized into three zones, *VIZ.* western, central, and eastern zones. The eastern zone is covered by the hilly areas of Chittagong Hill Tracts and is comparatively more stable than other zones (Ahmad, 2019; Thomas et al., 1992). A study by Hasan & Matin (2019) from the period 1989 to 2019 found that the central zone of the coastal area of Bangladesh was the most dynamic in terms of both erosion and accretion.

Sonadia Island situated along the Cox's Bazar coastal belt of the eastern zone is one of the emerging touristic islands where both the sandy sea beach and the mangrove vegetation, including the natural mangrove as well as plantation can be found. However, there has been very limited research on the coastal erosion-accretion and the degradation of the dunes on this island and the impact of the sea level rise (SLR), and coastal vegetation on accretion and erosion trend. Only very few studies were found in the literature, like; the distribution of heavy minerals (Kabir et al., 2018), shoreline change along the Maheshkhali Island (Saddam et al., 2023), grain size of the

newly growing sand bar (Hoque et al., 2013), morphological change of the developing sand bar from 1972-2006 (Hoque et al., 2023), and plant diversity in the dunes of Sonadia (Arefin et al., 2017). In contrast, a relatively higher number of scientific publications are available on the qualitative and quantitative assessment of shoreline dynamics in other regions region of the country, like; shoreline dynamics at Kuakata Island (Uddin et al., 2023), Hatiya Island (Ghosh et al., 2015), Kutubdia island (Islam et al., 2014), Saint Martin Island (Hossen & Sultana, 2023), shoreline change along the southeastern coast (Arefin et al., 2017; Mahamud & Takewaka, 2018; Salman et al., 2018), and along the whole coast (Crawford et al., 2021; Mullick et al., 2020; Sarwar & Woodroffe, 2013; Shamsuzzoha & Ahamed, 2023). Thus, it is very crucial to know the changes in the shoreline of Sonadia Island and the impact of different actors like vegetation, SLR, and position and elevation of sandy dunes on the historical changes of the shoreline.

1.2 Rationale of the study

Sonadia Island is recognized as one of the vital biodiversity hotspots in Bangladesh (Kabir et al., 2018; Sinha, 2019). It hosts unique mangrove forests that differ from those in the Sundarbans and can thrive in high salinity conditions. This ecological significance led the government to designate Sonadia as an ecologically critical area (ECA) in 1999 under the Environmental Act of 1995 (Sinha, 2019). The Bangladeshi government recently canceled the Sonadia deep-sea port project, which was initially conceived in 2006. This decision was driven by the fact that the existing ports in Chittagong and Mongla were overcrowded and had shallow drafts, posing significant limitations (Ramachandran, 2020). The concerns about potential harm to Sonadia's biodiversity led to the abandonment of the deep-sea port project in 2014, following the enactment of the Sonadia Deep Sea Port Authority Act in 2012 (Ramachandran, 2020). In a new development, the Bangladesh Export Zone Authority (BEZA) now has plans to transform Sonadia Island into a prominent tourist attraction and foreign direct investment hub by 2030. The master plan allocates only 3% of the island for tourism activities (Farhat, 2022).

Therefore, it is essential to give special consideration to the protection of the plant and animal life on Sonadia Island, as highlighted in the study by Arefin et al. (2017). Additionally, examining the dynamics of the shoreline, which significantly contribute to environmental and biological preservation, can provide valuable insights. Such an investigation can also be beneficial for informing the government's future initiatives regarding Sonadia Island.

This study aims to examine the interactions between environmental factors, including SLR, tropical cyclones, and flooding, and human activities like coastal plantation, and their combined impact on erosion and accretion in Sonadia Island. It is imperative to comprehend the dynamics of shoreline, the role of vegetation, the location and structure of sandy dunes, and the potential SLR's effect on these dynamics before implementing any project in this ECA. Moreover, this research holds significant importance for policymakers and informs prudent decisions regarding the conservation and sustainable development of the Sonadia. The findings will contribute to the formulation of environmentally responsible and conservation-focused projects in Sonadia Island.

1.3 Objectives of the study

In alignment with the principal research aim, the following precise objectives were established to achieve the anticipated outcomes.

1. To ascertain shoreline accretion and erosion trends on Sonadia Island from 1972 to 2023 through the utilization of satellite and field survey data.
2. To investigate the effects of sea level rise (SLR), tropical cyclones, floods, and coastal vegetation on coastal erosion and accretion on Sonadia Island.
3. To examine the natural formation processes of sandy dunes, historical degradation patterns, and potential measures for restoration on Sonadia Island.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Status of the world beach environment

Beaches are already under threat from a wide range of human activities and this will increase in the 21st century (Brown & McLachlan, 2002; Schlacher et al., 2006, 2008). In addition to direct anthropogenic impacts on beaches, global climate change is predicted to have dramatic, widespread, and long-lasting consequences for the world's marine ecosystems, particularly when coastlines are retreating inland in response to rising sea levels (Feagin et al., 2005; Harley et al., 2006). Thus, management and conservation of the unique ecological features and processes of beaches have become critical and pressing issues (Schlacher et al., 2008).

Sandy dunes are eolian landforms that develop in coastal situations where an ample supply of loose, sand-sized sediment is available to be transported inland by the ambient winds (Martínez & Psuty, 2004). Coastal dunes have an intrinsic value related to their spatial and temporal dynamics at the sharp boundary between land and sea. Coastal dunes exist more extensively where areas of

Figure 1: Widespread distribution of world coastal dunes, the blue circle indicates the location of the study area (Adapted from: Martínez & Psuty, 2004).

persistent coastal sand supply and dominant onshore winds favor episodes of inland transport to create broad dune fields. Active as well as stabilized coastal dunes of various scales and morphologies are recognized as products of coastal dynamics (Schlacher et al., 2008). The global distribution of the coastal dunes and barrier Island were shown in Figure 1.

2.2 Status of beach environment in Bangladesh

Coastal erosion is a significant and global issue (Biswas & Islam, 2017), and Bangladesh is not out of that. The coastline of Bangladesh is 710 km long and is composed of the interface of various ecological and economic systems, including mangroves (the world's largest mangrove forest covers 6,017 km²), tidal flat, estuaries, sea grass, about 70 islands, accreted land, beaches, a peninsula, rural settlements, urban and industrial areas, and ports (Ahmad, 2019; Hossain, 2001; Iftekhar, 2006). The coastal zone of Bangladesh is geomorphologically and hydrologically dominated by the Ganges Brahmaputra Meghna (GBM) river system and the Bay of Bengal. The coastal zone of Bangladesh covers an area of 47,201 km², 32% of the country, being the landmass of 19 districts (Ahmad, 2019).

Shoreline changes are also a considerable coastal phenomenon in Bangladesh (Islam et al., 2020; Salauddin et al., 2018), as it exposes more threats to natural disasters for instance cyclones, tornadoes, storm surges, flooding, river bank, coastal erosion, and so on (Ali, 1996; Islam et al., 2020) due to its geographical location and geomorphic conditions (Ali, 1996; Choudhury, 1989; Haider et al., 1991; Islam et al., 2020).

Depending on geographic features, the coastal zone of Bangladesh consists of three parts (Figure 2), a. The eastern zone b. The central zone, c. Western zone. The eastern region is covered by a hilly area that is more stable in comparison to the other two zones (Ahmad, 2019; Thomas et al., 1992). A study by Hasan & Matin (2019) from the period 1989 to 2019 found that the central zone was found to be the most dynamic in terms of both erosion and accretion. The western zone was mostly characterized by erosion, whereas only the eastern zone experienced a net land gain in this period.

Figure 2: Coastal zones of Bangladesh, showing eastern, central, and western zones (*Source: Hasan & Matin, 2019*).

2.3 Physical and ecological features of sandy beach

Sandy beaches worldwide are defined by their sand, wave, and tide regimes. Based on the physical and morphological appearance the beaches are classified as narrow and steep (reflective) to wide and flat (dissipative), as the sand becomes finer and waves and tides larger; most beaches are intermediate between these extremes. Dissipative beaches are erosional, whereas reflective beaches are accretional (Schlacher et al., 2008).

Figure 3: Typical features of a dynamic beach system (*Source: Kidd, 2001*).

According to Schlacher et al. (2008), the sandy beach possesses the following ecological features; Sandy beaches lack attached plants in their intertidal zone. Dissipative surf zones harbor unique phytoplankton species, integral to local food webs. Reflective beaches support fewer species, mainly robust crustaceans. Sandy beach surf zones (Figure 3) are vital nurseries and foraging grounds for fish, hosting rich zooplankton populations, including shrimps and prawns. These beaches are essential nesting sites for marine turtles and shorebirds, highlighting their importance in coastal biodiversity. Figure 3 shows the different features of a dynamic beach system including most active swash zone, surf zone, nearshore zone and different vegetation zones.

2.4 Role of coastal ecosystem

Beaches are dynamic landscapes comprised of unconsolidated material affected by wave and wind forces and ocean currents. The parent material that forms the beach may be rock, sand, gravel, pebbles, cobblestones, shells, coral, or others (Marshall & Banks, 2013). Beaches and dunes are elements of the same sedimentary system, where well-developed foredunes are only present in beaches with a sediment budget in equilibrium or accretion (Alcántara-Carrió et al., 2005; Botero et al., 2017).

The preservation of the coastal environment, such as beaches and the associated dune systems, generates economic benefits for the tourism and service sectors of the municipalities. Foredunes also play an important role in the protection of urban structures, such as streets and constructions,

against back sweeps, floods, and storm waves. Additionally, foredunes act as a transitional environment between the beach and the urban structures, providing a natural buffer zone against the action of storm waves, aerosols, and wind-blown sediments (Botero et al., 2017). According to Anonymous (2023), Sandy dunes in the coastal environment play a crucial role: they act as natural safeguards during floods, protect inland areas from high-energy storms, provide vital resources for diverse wildlife, and aid in replenishing eroded beach sand.

In sandy beach ecosystems, the top consumers within the food web consist of fish and avian species. These beaches are vital foraging grounds for higher vertebrates, including commercially valuable organisms like crabs and oysters, as well as species of conservation importance such as birds and turtles. Furthermore, there is a close and intricate interaction between the beach and adjacent coastal dunes, both in terms of physical and biological connections (Schlacher et al., 2008).

2.5 Natural formation process of coastal dunes

A dune is a mound of sand that is formed by the wind, usually along the beach or in a desert through the aggregation of the sand at the time of aeolian movement into a sheltered area behind an obstacle (Anonymous, 2023; Cornish, 1897; Lü et al., 2018; Martínez & Psuty, 2004). The common obstacle in a coastal area is macrophyte wrack, comprised mainly of the dead smooth cordgrass from the marsh (Anonymous, 2023). The wrack is an important energy source to the beach ecosystem and is assimilated into the beach ecosystem via two pathways into trophic webs: decomposition and incorporation and also works as the habitat for macrofauna (Marshall & Banks, 2013). The wrack traps the sand and then decomposes providing nutrients for germinating windblown seeds from sea oats, railroad vines, and other coastal dune plants that stabilize and hold the loose sand in place (Anonymous, 2023).

During these natural processes, a diverse community of organisms, including bacteria, yeasts, fungi, nematodes, invertebrate larvae, mites, as well as macrofauna, finds shelter and engage in nutrient cycling and decomposition (Marshall & Banks, 2013; Speed, 2005). Higher elevation dunes form on beaches from wind and the sand-trapping process of vegetation. The above-ground portions of plants increase friction to wind. This causes the deposition of aeolian sand, particularly on the foredune. However, on developed and man-made beaches, dunes may not be present because the vegetation has been removed or destroyed (Marshall & Banks, 2013).

2.6 Degradation process of dunes

Coastal dunes are degraded and lost because of a wide array of human actions and activities (Lithgow et al., 2013; Nordstrom, 2021) which can be aggregated into six groups: 1) housing and recreation; 2) industrial and commercial use; 3) waste disposal; 4) agriculture; 5) mining and 6) military activities. Typically, they alter coastal dynamics and natural processes, eliminate topographic variability, fragment, degrade or eliminate habitats, reduce biodiversity, and threaten endemic species (Ayyad, 2003; De Luca et al., 2011; Faggi & Dadon, 2011; Lithgow et al., 2013; Martinez et al., 2006; Nordstrom, 2021; Waikato, 2006)

In case of natural causes, strong winds and associated waves generate waves which can cause a flattening of the beach profile and may form scarps on the beach berm and erosion of dunes (Marshall & Banks, 2013). Back sweeps have been defined as a major cause of erosion for the marine face of the dunes (Portz et al., 2018). This sequence of strong back sweeps caused an intense loss of sediment from the face of the foredunes to the lower shore face, creating a negative sediment budget that makes difficult the natural reconstruction of the dunes (Botero et al., 2017). Erosion of the foredune systems occurs quickly under the influence of winds and storm waves, resulting in the formation of scarps and deflation corridors (Botero et al., 2017; Hesp, 2002).

2.7 Restoration of degraded dunes

Restoration and preservation of coastal dunes are urgently needed because of the increasingly rapid loss and degradation of these ecosystems due to many human activities (Lithgow et al., 2013). Dunes are not static, as they are made of sand and are in a constant state of change. Dune vegetation is vital to the building and stability of the dunes as they have extensive root systems that help to stabilize the dunes (Anonymous, 2023).

Based on the application of so many processes like; artificial seaweed, amino acid application, dewatering, etc. were found as not effective for controlling beach erosion. However, the most cost-effective method of holding sand on beaches was found to protect the natural beach's physical environment and habitat (Marshall & Banks, 2013). Restored vegetation is likely to act as a stabilizing agent in dune systems; however, there is virtually no scientific knowledge on the impact of plants on dune erosion and protective capabilities during storms (Sigren et al., 2014). Results from a small-scale mobile-bed wave flume experiment by Sigren et al. (2014) with live plants

clearly showed that the presence of the plants significantly reduced the volume of dune erosion and the dune scarp retreat rate by over 30%.

Finally, it is important to acknowledge that there is no perfect restoration job or assessment, but we can improve it. The theory of ecological succession provides a theoretical background for restoration and emphasizes the role of natural disturbance as a key element of community dynamics (Grainger et al., 2011; Lithgow et al., 2013)

2.8 Potential restoration measures of degraded dunes

Based on the intensive review of the literature the following measures were found as effective measures for the restoration of sandy beaches in the global perspective. However, the exact measures may vary based on local factors.

2.8.1 Installation of Sand Fences

The principal function of a dune-forming fence is to reduce the wind velocity, thereby causing drift sand to be deposited in the vicinity of the fence (Figure 4) and contributing to the increase of

Figure 4: Accumulation of sediment using sand fences (*Source: Botero et al., 2017; Kidd, 2001*)

sand volume and average width of the dune (Botero et al., 2017; Kidd, 2001). This structure is particularly useful in environmentally or culturally sensitive areas where it is undesirable to use earthmoving equipment or where access is difficult (Kidd, 2001). Moreover, sand fencing is a low-cost, easy-to-install, and effective way to improve the sediment budget of the foredune (Botero et al., 2017).

2.8.2 Managing Washouts

Washouts are very susceptible areas to erosion and consequently, they need specific management actions (Botero et al., 2017; McKann et al., 1991; Portz et al., 2015). Interventions in washout areas occur in situations of erosion on the beach face or on the dune system, caused by the increased flow during excessive rain episodes (Botero et al., 2017).

2.8.3 Managing threat

According to Jones et al. (2009), the primary threats to the world's beaches include climate-change, erosion, nourishment, shoreline hardening, off-road vehicles, beach cleaning, pollution, fisheries, sand removal (mining), and introduced species, etc. Botero et al. (2017), mentioned that the coastal dunes are degraded due to the destruction of coastal vegetation by construction works, the removal of coral reefs for jewelry making and decoration, and interference in the marine dynamics by misplaced breakwaters and jetties. Proper management of the potential threats would be a very effective measure to restore the degraded dunes.

2.8.4 Beach Nourishment

Beach nourishment is the foremost soft shore protection technique, and it concerns the placement of aggregates on the beach profile to oppose coastal erosion. Nourishment is also used to expand or create a beach for tourist use (Botero et al., 2017).

2.8.5 Macrophyte wrack

The term for seaweed, cordgrass, driftwood, and other organic materials produced by coastal ecosystems that wash ashore on the beach (Anonymous, 2023). Seaweed that washes ashore (wrack) may stay in the beach environment where it promotes dune formation or becomes part of terrestrial or marine food webs (Marshall & Banks, 2013)

2.8.6 Erosion control by protective vegetation

Control of wind erosion on coastal dunes relies primarily on maintaining a uniform protective cover of suitable vegetation (Kidd, 2001). Vegetated dunes have high aesthetic value and are likely to be more resilient to wave-induced erosion (Sigren et al., 2014). The plants and animals that live in coastal areas are adapted to harsh conditions such as water logging and dehydration, excess salt, infertile soil, wind damage, and shifting sands (Waikato, 2006). The native vegetation has an important role in stabilizing the dunes, imprisoning the sediments carried by the wind, and fixating large areas of dunes, thereby keeping the sand in the dune-beach system (Botero et al., 2017; Cordazzo et al., 2006).

Figure 5: Pathway and footbridge installed to access the beach (*Source: Botero et al., 2017*)

2.8.7 Controlled Accesses to Protect Sensitive Dune Habitats

The access of users to the beach damages the dunes environment, particularly, due to the trampling of the vegetation and the formation of blowouts (Botero et al., 2017; Stephenson, 1999). The use of a footbridge (Figure 5) and a specific pathway (Figure 5) for entrance may help the restoration process.

2.9 Techniques generally used for the assessment of the coastal dynamics

In the realm of coastal dynamics assessment, various techniques are employed to examine shoreline changes, which occur across diverse time scales and are influenced by factors like waves, tides, periodic storms, sea level rise (SLR), and human development activities (Addo et al., 2008; Jayanthi et al., 2018). One prominent tool in shoreline change detection analysis is satellite remote sensing, which has made significant advancements, offering an extensive archive of historical data on a regional scale. This data helps establish a fixed baseline from a distant past, enabling a clearer understanding of changes and the determination of alterations to the shoreline (Shamsuzzoha & Ahamed, 2023). Moreover, many coastal nations have undertaken studies on shoreline changes, employing either traditional mapping methods or digital shoreline analysis systems (DSAS) (Alemayehu et al., 2015; Jayanthi et al., 2018; Joesidawati, 2016; Morton, 2008; To & Thao, 2008).

2.10 Remote sensing for coastal change monitoring

Remote sensing (RS) technology and Geographical Information Systems (GIS) play crucial roles in spatial decision-making at local and national levels. They are also essential for assessing shoreline changes over time and the potential impacts of sea-level rise projections (Ford, 2013; Jayanthi et al., 2018; Maiti & Bhattacharya, 2009). Various remote sensing materials, including Landsat images (Dominici et al., 2019; Ford, 2013), video images (Valentini et al., 2017), synthetic aperture radar (SAR) images (Bruno et al., 2016), and global positioning system (GPS) survey (Harley et al., 2011), have been widely employed for shoreline delineation and quantifying changes. Of these, Landsat images with a 30m resolution are freely accessible and particularly suitable for monitoring sandy areas with specific characteristics like deltas and large beaches with significant temporal variations (El-Asmar & Hereher, 2011; Ghosh et al., 2015; Matin & Hasan, 2021; Salman et al., 2018). Analyzing time series of satellite images allows for a detailed understanding of the nature and scale of changes occurring along the sandbar across the island's shoreline (Hoque et al., 2023).

2.11 Digital shoreline analysis system (DSAS) for shoreline change analysis

Various remote sensing methods have been applied for shoreline extraction and change assessment in several studies using multispectral satellite data (Ataol & Kale, 2022; Crawford et al., 2021; Dominici et al., 2019; Natarajan et al., 2021; Sarwar & Woodroffe, 2013; Shamsuzzoha & Ahamed, 2023). Most of the studies use DSAS for the analysis of the shoreline change rate using the automatic, semi-automatic, and manually digitized shoreline and baseline features (Alesheikh et al., 2007; Crawford et al., 2021; Das et al., 2021; Dominici et al., 2019; Hoque et al., 2023; Islam et al., 2014; Sarwar & Woodroffe, 2013). The Digital Shoreline Analysis System (DSAS) provides an automated method for establishing measurement locations, performs rate calculations, provides the statistical data necessary to assess the reliability of the rates, and includes a beta model for forecasting shoreline position (Himmelstoss et al., 2021).

CHAPTER THREE

MATERIAL AND METHODS

3.1 Description of the study area

Sonadia Island is situated on the southern coast of Bangladesh under the Cox's Bazar district and Maheshkhali Upazila with an area of 2249.29 hectares (Figure 6). The calculation of this area was conducted by the author during the study period through the application of semi-automatic digitization techniques. The extent of this Island is from 91°51'00'' to 91°55'30''E longitude and 21°28'30'' to 21°33'00''N latitude (Figure 6). The Government of Bangladesh declared this Island as an Ecologically Critical Area (ECA) in 1999 (Chowdhury et al., 2011). The Bara Canal separated this Island from the mainland of the Maheshkhali channel (Arefin et al., 2017).

Figure 6: The location of the study area is shown in reference to the global and country map.

3.1.1 Weather conditions of Sonadia Island

The soil of this Island is a mixture of sand and clay where the northern part shows comparatively clay with inundation by seawater and the southern part shows almost sandy soil. The average temperature of the island ranges from 16.1°C to 34.8°C and the altitude of this island ranges from 0-4 meters (DoE, 1999). The mean annual precipitation (Figure 7) of the study area varies from 2750mm/yr. (2009) to 4280mm/yr. (2015) from 2000 to 2020 (Huffman et al., 2019).

Figure 7: Monthly mean precipitation of the study area from 2001 to 2020, this graph is generated from the data monthly Global Precipitation Measurement raster data provided by NASA using Google Earth Engine.

3.1.2 Socio-economic conditions of Sonadia Island

Sonadia Island, home to approximately 1,176 residents, relies heavily on its natural resources, which include agriculture, shrimp fry collection, and fishing. The literacy rate on the island is exceptionally low at just 12.3%, and there are no indigenous communities. The majority of the population faces economic hardships and lacks enthusiasm for education, with around 40% of the people engaged in fishing, salt farming, and agriculture (Rabbi, 2016). The island spans 10,298 hectares and encompasses various features like coastal and mangrove plantations, salt production fields, shrimp farms, agricultural areas, and human settlements (Arefin et al., 2017). Sonadia Island

is known for its abundant natural resources, particularly its potential to supply fish not only for domestic consumption but also for the entire country (Roy et al., 2021).

3.1.3 Biodiversity of Sonadia Island

The biodiversity of Sonadia Island is characterized by the presence of planted mangroves on mudflats, with *Avicennia alba* and *Avicennia marina* being the predominant species at most sites. The location sustains the sole surviving fragment of remnant natural mangrove forest in the southeastern region of Bangladesh (Rabbi, 2016). Research has identified 138 species from 121 genera and 52 families, categorized as trees, shrubs, herbs, and climbers (Arefin et al., 2017). The island supports a diverse range of wildlife, including water birds, mollusks, echinoderms, and marine turtles (Roy et al., 2021).

Figure 8: Status of the plantation program at Sonadia Island with respective area and year up to 2023.

3.1.4 Land use pattern at Sonadia Island

Sonadia Island hosts the only remaining mangrove vegetation in southeast Bangladesh, a significant ecological feature that used to span the Chittagong and Cox's Bazar coastlines (Roy et al., 2021). The predominant land use patterns on the island are as follows: homestead vegetation covers 78% of the area, followed by roadside areas at 23%, cultivated land at 10%, mangroves at 9%, sandy beaches at 4%, and wetlands at 1% (Arefin et al., 2017). Figure 8 shows the different years and respective plantations area including the Jhau (*Casuarina equisetifolia*), Raintree (*Albizia saman*) and Akashmoni (*Acacia auriculiformis*). Jhau were planted at shoreline and Raintree and the Akashmoni at homestead and inland areas.

3.1.5 Nature of the coastal environment

Sonadia Island is a unique coastal environment. Unlike deltaic and estuarine mouth bars, it operates as a sub-maridional bar along a cliff coast, acting as a protective barrier island to the southwest of Maheshkhali Island. This low-lying coastline is exposed to the sea, featuring extensive dunes that run along the entire shoreline and reach several hundred meters inland (Kabir et al., 2018).

3.2 Methodological framework of the study

The primary objective of the present study is to investigate coastal dynamics, specifically focusing on the erosion and accretion of the shoreline, within the time frame spanning from 1972 to 2023. Additionally, the study seeks to assess the influence of various factors, such as sea level rise (SLR), coastal plantation, tropical cyclones, floods, the spatial distribution of dunes along the coastal profile, the number of dunes, and the elevation of dunes, on the processes of coastal erosion and accretion. To achieve these objectives, the research employs dumpy level and GPS surveys across the entirety of Sonadia Island's coastal area.

The methodology involves the utilization of band ratio techniques and a semi-automatic shoreline digitization procedure to generate shoreline data for different years, derived from Landsat satellite imagery of the Sonadia coast. Subsequently, the study employs the Digital Shoreline Analysis System (DSAS) tools to estimate erosion and accretion rates based on baseline and shoreline data. Following this analysis, statistical tests are conducted to discern the potential impacts of the aforementioned factors on coastal erosion and accretion. The complete workflow, including all these steps, is visually represented in Figure 9.

3.3 Collection of Beach Profile Data

To collect the data regarding the relative position and the height of the dunes and other objects in the beach area, the current study conducted a dumpy-level survey. A total of ten transects across the beach (From the drift line toward the land) were taken to find out the preliminary positions of the dunes including other beach objects. The dumpy level survey was selected for this study as this level provides centimeter-level accuracy of the relative height of the dunes. Due to the lack of high-resolution Digital Elevation Model (DEM) data or Lidar source data, it was the best option for this study. The survey was conducted from 24 August 2023 to 28 August 2023 throughout Sonadia Island.

Figure 9: Research framework for the analysis of the coastal erosion and accretion and impact of different actors on the coastal dynamics.

3.3.1 Dumpy level survey

A Dumpy level is a widely used surveying instrument that is used to measure the relative vertical distance or height of different points with known horizontal distances. The whole set-up of dumpy-level instruments consists of a telescope, tripod, vertical spindle, compass, and tribrach plate

(Figure 10&11) (Shahjahan & Aziz, 2013). Major parts of an optical dumpy level are shown in Figure 10, these include the following:

1. Focusing Screws,
2. Telescope,
3. Objective lens
4. Compass
5. Foot/Levelling Screws
6. Eye-Piece
7. Leveling bubble
8. Leveling head
9. Foot/Base Plate

Figure 10: Major parts of a dumpy-level instrument (Source: *civilread.com*).

The telescope uses its focusing capacity to read the distant reading of the leveling staff, it can be rotated 360 degrees in the horizontal direction with the help of a vertical spindle. The bubble tube is used for the vertical adjustment of the instruments with the horizontal plane, with an exact adjustment the vertical axis of the telescope makes a right angle with the horizontal plane or line of collimation (Shahjahan & Aziz, 2013). Garmin Map 62S GPS (Figure 11) was used for tracking the shoreline along the drift line and measuring tape (Figure 11) was used for taking transect distance across the beach.

Figure 11: Instruments used during the field survey, a) A dumpy level (Source: ebay.co.uk); b) A tripod stand used to support the level on its top (Source: amazon.in); c) Levelling staff used to collect elevation measurements (Source: nedogroup.net); d) Tribrach plate used to the horizontal level of the instrument (Source: civilengpro.com); e) Measuring tape used for transect distance measuring (Source: thattoolplace.com); f) Garmin 64S GPS (Source: bdstall.com).

3.3.2 Taking Staff Reading

The first measurement that is taken from the first setup of the instruments is called back reading (BR), which is used to calculate the height of the instrument (HI) from which all other reduced levels (RL) are calculated. The points taken at last from a setup of the instrument are called Fore

reading (FR), and all other readings taken between the BR and FR are called Intermediate reading (IR). In case of a change in the instrument position, e.g., 2nd setup of the instrument take the reading of the FR of the first setup as BR, this is called a changed point (Andysupa, 2016; Bettess, 1998; Shahjahan & Aziz, 2013).

3.3.3 Line of collimation method to determine the reduced level

The elevation or reduced level (RL) of the line of collimation (LC) or height of the instrument (HI) of every setup of the dumpy levels is obtained by calculating the RL using benchmark (BM) height. The height of the LC is obtained by adding the staff reading with the BM of the site (Figure 12). RL of all the other IR is obtained by subtracting the staff reading from the HI. In case of the change point (Figure 12) for a new setup of the instrument, a new HI is obtained by adding the difference of the new BR and the most recent FR (BR-FR) of the same point with the RL of the previous LC. The same process is continued till the end of the survey (Andysupa, 2016; Shahjahan & Aziz, 2013).

Figure 12: Process of dumpy level setup at the field and direction of taking the reading

3.3.4 Benchmark selection

A benchmark (BM) is a point on the ground having a known elevation which may be used as the basis for measuring the relative height/elevation of a place or geographical location. Generally, there are four types of BM 1) Great Trigonometrical Survey (G.T.S), 2) Permanent, 3) Arbitrary, and 4) Temporary (Shahjahan & Aziz, 2013). If there is no available BM near the study site a temporary/arbitrary BM can be taken to calculate the RL of the surveying points (Andysupa, 2016). The current study takes a 2m arbitrary BM for the calculation of the RL of the HI and all other readings.

3.3.5 Arithmetic check of calculated reduced level

To calculate the RL of the readings and the correctness of the survey the following formula is used according to Shahjahan & Aziz (2013).

The method used to calculate the RL of a point

$$HC = RL_{BM} + BR$$

$$RL = HC - BR$$

$$RL = HC - FR$$

$$RL = HC - IR$$

HC: height of instrument

RLBM: Reduce Level of Benchmark

BR: Back reading

RL: Reduced level

FR: Fore reading

IR: Intermediate reading

The method used to check the accuracy of the work

$$\sum_{i=1}^n BR - \sum_{i=1}^n FR$$

$$= \text{Last RL} - \text{First RL}$$

$\sum_{i=1}^n BR$: Sum of all BR

$\sum_{i=1}^n FR$: Sum of all FR

3.4 Beach profiling

Beach profiles are generated using a simple line graph and then showing the relative positions of different beach objects like dunes, canals, *Ipomoea pes-caprae*, *Vitex trifolia*, *Casuarina equisetifolia* (Jhau), etc. in the profile based on their horizontal and vertical position. A total of ten beach profiles were generated starting with transect 1 from the north point to transect 10 at the south point to get the preliminary profile of the coast of this Island. Geo-location of the transect were shown in Table 1.

Table 1: GPS location of ten transects of Sonadia island.

Transect No.	Initial point (Decimal degrees)		Ending point (Decimal degrees)	
	Latitude	Longitude	Latitude	Longitude
1	21.53972	91.84049	21.53981	91.84097
2	21.52653	91.84624	21.52653	91.84624
3	21.51258	91.85211	21.51286	91.85246
4	21.50474	91.85984	21.50585	91.86105
5	21.49964	91.86541	21.50075	91.86669
6	21.49123	91.87346	21.49178	91.87405
7	21.88624	91.87976	21.48716	91.88071
8	21.47591	91.89331	21.47716	91.89468
9	21.47715	91.92352	21.47736	91.92293
10	21.58790	91.93434	21.48807	91.93386

3.5 Shoreline tracking using GPS

GPS tracking was used during the field survey to generate field-based shoreline delineation. For this purpose, after 50-100m intervals latitude and longitude readings of coordinates were taken to demarcate the drift line (Figure 13). The drift line was taken as the high tide swash zone during the survey. The tracking procedure takes three days to cover the whole beach around 20km in length from 25-26 August 2023.

Figure 13: High tide swash zone debris indicating the drift line for the different tidal levels (The left drift line was the high tide swash zone on 25 August 2023).

3.6 Band ratio Techniques to determine historical shoreline

The current study uses the Landsat 1 and 3 MSS, Landsat 4 and 5 TM, and Landsat 8 OLI images to cover the temporal coverage from 1972 to 2023. Landsat images were chosen as it has higher temporal coverage with a free large data archive with a spatial resolution (30m×30m) (Gümüs et al., 2021). All of the satellite images were stacked, filtered, and processed using Google Earth Engine (GEE) API, as it provides cloud computing of the diverse remote sensing data. A band ratio (BR) technique was used by the study to differentiate the water and land from the remote sensing images as the raw images cannot determine the land and water transition point (Figure 14a). This BR techniques divide the value of a pixel having a higher reflectance band value with the value of the same pixel with a lower reflectance band value (Gümüs et al., 2021; Kayadibi & Aydal, 2013) and differentiate land and water transition zone (Figure 14b). The current study performed the BR techniques by the ratio of Band 6/ Band 3 for OLI images, Band 5/ Band2 for TM images, and Band 6/ Band4 for MSS images.

Figure 14: Shoreline extracted by band ratio techniques for the year 2023 using Landsat OLI images: a) Overlying of the extracted shoreline with the natural color RGB composite of OLI images, 2023; b) Overlying of the extracted shoreline with the band ratio raster.

Table 2: Description of the satellite images used for the study.

Satellite and Sensor	Band Description	Wavelength (μm)	Acquisition data	Cloud Cover (%)	Path/ Row	Resolution (m)
Landsat OLI/TIRS	8- B6 (shortwave infrared)	1.566-1.651	2023/01/11	0.01	136/45	30
Landsat OLI/TIRS	8- B3 (green)	0.533-0.590	2023/01/11	0.01	136/45	30
Landsat OLI/TIRS	8- B6 (shortwave infrared)	1.566-1.651	2014/02/03	0.13	136/45	30

Satellite and Sensor	Band Description	Wavelength (μm)	Acquisition data	Cloud Cover (%)	Path/ Row	Resolution (m)
Landsat OLI/TIRS	8- B3 (green)	0.533-0.590	2014/02/03	0.13	136/45	30
Landsat TM	5- B5 (shortwave infrared)	1.55-1.75	2005/02/10	0	136/45	30
Landsat TM	5- B2 (green)	0.52-0.60	2005/02/10	0	136/45	30
Landsat TM	5- B5 (shortwave infrared)	1.55-1.75	1999/02/26	0	136/45	30
Landsat TM	5- B2 (green)	0.52-0.60	1999/02/26	0	136/45	30
Landsat TM	5- B5 (shortwave infrared)	1.55-1.75	1996/02/18	0	136/45	30
Landsat TM	5- B2 (green)	0.52-0.60	1996/02/18	0	136/45	30
Landsat TM	5- B5 (shortwave infrared)	1.55-1.75	1991/12/05	0	136/45	30
Landsat TM	5- B2 (green)	0.52-0.60	1991/12/05	0	136/45	30
Landsat TM	4- B5 (shortwave infrared)	1.55-1.75	1989/02/26	0	136/45	30
Landsat TM	4- B2 (green)	0.52-0.60	1989/02/22	0	136/45	30
Landsat MSS	3- B6 (near infrared)	0.7 - 0.8	1979/01/19	0	146/45	60
Landsat MSS	3- B4 (green)	0.5 - 0.6	1979/01/19	0	146/45	60
Landsat MSS	1- B6 (near infrared)	0.7 - 0.8	1972/12/27	0	146/45	60

Satellite and Sensor	Band Description	Wavelength (μm)	Acquisition data	Cloud Cover (%)	Path/ Row	Resolution (m)
Landsat MSS	1- B4 (green)	0.5 - 0.6	1972/12/27	0	146/45	60

3.6.1 Post-processing of the band ratio Geo-TIFF

After pre-processing, all of the satellite images were downloaded as Geo-TIFF files from the Google Earth Engine (GEE) and imported to ArcGIS 10.8 software for further processing. The whole process of the post-analysis of the band ratio (BR) raster to generate the respective shoreline is given in Figure 15. Determination of the exact position of the shoreline is somewhat difficult as the coastal area is the most dynamic zone in nature. However, it would be possible to generate shorelines both manually, semi-automatically, and automatically (Islam et al., 2014). The current study delineates the shoreline using a semi-automatic process based on BR raster images. The study by Alesheikh et al., (2007) found BR techniques showed an efficient identification of the shoreline position using remote sensing techniques.

This process of delineating shorelines uses ArcGIS spatial analysis, conversion, and data management tools to generate each shoreline position polyline. First of all, BR geo-TIFF images were converted into binary images using a simple formula in ArcGIS “If the value of $B6/B3 < 1$ then 1 else 0 algorithm” for Landsat 8 OLI satellite images, the formula is used for Landsat 5 TM and Landsat 4 TM images in the form of “If the value of $B5/B2 < 1$ then 1 else 0 algorithm” and for Landsat 3 MSS and Landsat 1 MSS images in the form of “If the value of $B6/B4 < 1$ then 1 else 0 algorithm”. Band and their wavelength details are shown in Table 1. After that, the binary images having values 0 (Not land) or 1 (land), which have an exact separation between the land and water line (Figure 15) were converted into a polygon (Figure 15) to generate the shoreline boundaries. To generate a shoreline the polygon covering the land was converted into a polyline and then split the polyline at the most northern and southern part of the Island to get continuous shoreline data. Then, the polyline was dissolved to get a continuous and a single shoreline. This process was repeated for each of the BR images to generate shorelines for the years 2023, 2014, 2005, 1999, 1996, 1991, 1989, 1979, and 1972.

Figure 15: Semi-automatic digitization process of the shoreline using band ratio (BR) raster data in ArcGIS.

3.7 Digital Shoreline Analysis System

DSAS version 1.0 was developed by USGS in 1992 and version 5.1 was released in November 2021 and is available as an Add-in for the ArcGIS 10.4+ version. Algorithms of these tools allow us to calculate the change distance, change statistics over time, and forecast the future shorelines for 10 years and 20 years (Himmelstoss et al., 2021; Zambrano-Medina et al., 2023). The analysis of the shoreline change by DSAS is considered one of the most efficient and effective as the algorithm of this tool has higher performance in shoreline change analysis in comparison to other tools and methods (Baig et al., 2020).

3.7.1 Formatting shoreline and baseline attribute field

DSAS has its specific requirement of the field to calculate the rate of change of the shoreline and baseline for example it needs a projected coordinate system, the shoreline measurement value at a meter, and so on. Shoreline shapefile attribute field requirements are mentioned in Table 2 and Table 3 shows the Baseline attribute table requirements according to the guidelines of field manuals of DSAS user manual 5.1 (Himmelstoss et al., 2021).

Table 3: Shoreline features attribute table requirement for DSAS analysis according to the user manual of DSAS 5.1.

Field name	Data type	Requirement
Object_ID	Object identifier	Auto-generated
Shape	Geometry	Auto-generated
Shape_length	Double	Auto-generated
Date	Text	User-defined
Uncertainty	Numeric	User-defined
Shoreline_type	Text	User-defined

Table 4: Baseline features attribute table requirement for DSAS analysis according to the user manual of DSAS 5.1.

Field name	Data type	Requirement
Object_ID	Object identifier	Auto-generated
Shape	Geometry	Auto-generated
Shape_length	Double	Auto-generated
ID	Long integer	User-defined
Group	Long integer	User-defined
Search Distance	Double	User-defined

3.7.2 Casting transect line

At first, all inputs shoreline including baseline were projected into the Projected Coordinate System (PCS) using WGS 1984 UTM Zone 46N, as DSAS required it for distance measurement. After adding all required attributes at the shoreline and baseline table transects were cast. To cast transect the study used a distance of 50m (Figure 16) interval along the beach and a maximum search distance of 2000m, A smoothing distance of 500m was used to get the orthogonal transects from the baseline toward the sea by intersecting each shoreline by each transect.

Figure 16: Example of DSAS transect (across the beach), baseline, and shoreline position (along the beach).

3.8 Change measurement and statistical analysis

Net shoreline movement (NSM) and Shoreline change envelope (SCE) were used by DSAS to calculate the distance of different shorelines over time. Endpoint rate (EPR), LRR Linear regression rate (LRR), and Weighted linear regression rate (WLR) are very common statistics used for the analysis of the shoreline change rate by DSAS. Each method used the distance of shoreline positions from the baseline with time intervals and the final change rate expressed as a meter per year and change distance as a meter (Himmelstoss et al., 2021). DSAS calculate all type of distance along the transect for all shoreline (i.e., 1972, 1979, 1989, 1991, 1996, 1999, 2024, and 2023) using the distance of intersection points of the shoreline and each transect.

3.8.1 Net Shoreline Movement

The net shoreline movement (NSM) is the perpendicular distance of the youngest and the oldest shorelines at the intersection points of all transects (Himmelstoss et al., 2021). NSM is calculated using the following equation, where D is the shoreline distance from the baseline calculated as a meter.

$$NSM = D_{\text{Youngest}} - D_{\text{Oldest}}$$

Here,

NSM = Net Shoreline Movement

D_{Youngest} = Distance of most recent shoreline from baseline

D_{Oldest} = Distance of the oldest shoreline from baseline

3.8.2 Shoreline Change Envelope

The shoreline change envelope (SCE) is the greatest distance among all shorelines calculated without considering the shoreline date. SCE only considers two shorelines one is the nearest to the baseline and the other is the farthest from the baseline. This distance is always positive regardless of erosion and accretion (Himmelstoss et al., 2021). NSM only considers the most recent and eldest shoreline for measuring the distance, on the other hand, SCE considers the highest distance eroded or accreted at the coast (Figure 17).

3.8.3 End Point Rate

The endpoint rate (EPR) is calculated by dividing the NSM value by the time interval of the oldest and the youngest shoreline (Himmelstoss et al., 2021). EPR is calculated using the following equation.

$$EPR = \frac{NSM}{T_{\text{Youngest}} - T_{\text{Oldest}}}$$

Here,

EPR= End Point Rate,

NSM = Net Shoreline Movement.

T_{Youngest} = Shoreline date of the youngest one

T_{oldest} = Shoreline date of the oldest one

Figure 17: All shoreline data along the transect 181, net shoreline movement (NSM) the distance between shoreline 1972 and 2023, and shoreline change envelope (SCE) the distance between nearest (1989) and farthest (2023) shoreline from baseline.

3.8.4 Linear Regression Rate

The linear regression rate (LRR) is the slope of the regression line representing the intersecting points of all shorelines and their distance from the baseline (Himmelstoss et al., 2021). It is a linear regression statistical method that uses a linear equation to get the best-fit model of the rate of change with time (Das et al., 2021; Kuleli et al., 2011; Zambrano-Medina et al., 2023). LRR used the following regression model to get the linear rate of change of shoreline.

$$Y = aX + b$$

Here,

Y = Distance in meters from the baseline,

X = Shoreline date in year,

a = Slope of the regression line (m/year) representing LRR, and

b = Constant representing the Y-axis intercept.

The positive value of slope indicates the accretion of the coastline line and the negative value of slope indicates the erosion of the coastline, the higher the slope value the greater the rate of change. LRR is very suitable for the longer period change analysis of the coastline change (Zambrano-Medina et al., 2023). Finally, DSAS calculates the N number of LRR for the N number of transect and takes the mean rate of all LRR as the overall rate of change in linear regression.

3.8.5 Weighted Linear Regression

Weighted Linear Regression (WLR) is also a linear regression line, which is a better-fit line than the line of LRR, as it considers the 95% confidence interval to generate a regression line (Genz et al., 2007). According to (Himmelstoss et al., 2021) the weight (w) of the WLR is a variance function determined by the uncertainty of the measurement during shoreline extraction to rate change calculation. The weight value w is calculated using the following equation, where the uncertainty e is calculated using the uncertainty field value of the shoreline feature class, which is given at the time of the DSAS statistical analysis procedure (Godwyn-Paulson et al., 2021; Himmelstoss et al., 2021).

$$W = \frac{1}{e^2}$$

Here,

W = Weight of the linear regression

e = Variance function determined by the uncertainty of the measurement

3.9 Climate change impact model on coastal erosion

The current study chose the Bruun rule (Bruun, 1962) to estimate the direct impact of the sea level rise (SLR) due to global warming on coastal erosion. We know that SLR is not only a single conversion method of mass and volume nearshore, it's a complex process of the interaction of different factors like river discharge, sediment flow from upland, local subsidence, and the effect of coastal vegetation (Lee, 2013). However, this model is a simple two-dimensional mass conservational method taking assumptions that the coastal profile will exist in equilibrium conditions although the SLR occurs shortly. Although the assumptions and simplifications of these rules have been controversial matters for the last two decades, this is the only present method that can estimate coastal erosion due to the SLR in an efficient way (Athanasidou et al., 2020; Cooper & Pilkey, 2004). Bruun rule can be expressed by the following equation:

$$R = \frac{SLR_{\Delta t}}{\tan(\beta)}$$

$$\tan(\beta) = \frac{\tan(\beta_1) + \tan(\beta_2) + \tan(\beta_3) + \dots + \tan(\beta_n)}{n}$$

Here,

R = Horizontal erosion of the shoreline due to SLR,

$SLR_{\Delta t}$ = Sea level rise due to global warming within the period of Δt ,

$\tan(\beta)$ = Active slope of the beach profile,

n = Number of profiles used for the calculation of nearshore mean profile.

Bruun described the active profile slope as the slope between the beach area up to that level beyond which there has not shown any significant change in time (Bruun, 1962), which is known as the nearshore slope. If the SLR shows a negative value then there will not be any coastal erosion at the nearshore (Athanasidou et al., 2020). According to an IPCC report in 2009, the average rate of SLR in Bangladesh was 5mm per year (Uzzaman, 2014), and according to (Lee, 2013) the SLR was 4.46 mm/yr. from 1990 to 2009. Another study (Singh, 2002), based on 22 years of tidal data found that the SLR at the eastern coast of Bangladesh faced almost twice the erosion rate of 7.8 mm/yr. However, the current study used both of these rates to calculate coastal erosion due to SLR. The slope of the active near shore of Sonadia Island was calculated based on the average slope of ten nearshore profiles (Equation x) which was taken by a dumpy level survey on 24-28 August 2023. Slope $\tan(\beta_n)$ was calculated by dividing the vertical shift (h) of the elevation profile by the horizontal distance (d) of the drift line point and offshore point.

3.10 Shoreline Forecast using Kalman Filter

For the forecasting of the shoreline, the study used the Kalman filter model (Kalman, 1960), which is also a part of the DSAS 5.1 Add-in plugin used a minimum of four historical shorelines to predict the 10 and 20 years of future shoreline positions with the uncertainty bands (Himmelstoss et al., 2021; Long & Plant, 2012). Kalman filter is a statistically developed method and it requires a linear regression rate to predict the future position of the shoreline. The model minimizes the observed error at the time of running the forecasting shoreline position (Long & Plant, 2012; Zambrano-Medina et al., 2023). The model begins with the oldest shoreline and estimates each successive

year's shoreline position and after finding the subsequent shoreline year the model validates the predicted shoreline position with the observed shoreline position at that year. This process is repeated up to the most recent shoreline position estimation prediction, and validation, by this process this filter minimizes the prediction error with the validation of the observed shoreline data. Finally, Kalman filter develop a fit model to predict 10 year and 20 years future shoreline position (Godwyn-Paulson et al., 2021; Himmelstoss et al., 2021; Long & Plant, 2012; Zambrano-Medina et al., 2023).

Kalman filter is a statistically developed, simple, efficient, and widely used method for the assimilation of the observed data in modeling for nonlinear applications (Long & Plant, 2012). However, when the shoreline data represented a well-fit linear regression line, Kalman filter-based forecasting may look like the extrapolated line of the linear regression line (Himmelstoss et al., 2021).

3.11 Effect of Tropical Cyclone and coastal plantation on beach erosion

Due to its geographical location, the coastal region of Bangladesh has been subject to tropical cyclones almost every year since 1582. Generally, the cyclone is affected either in early summer from April to May, or the late rainy season from October to November (Hossain & Mullick, 2020). The study includes the two devastating cyclones to estimate their impact on shoreline erosion and accretion, one is the devastating cyclone on April 29, 1991, which caused the death of 150,000 people and 70,000 cattle in Patuakhali-Cox's Bazar coast and the other was the cyclone on 19 May 1997, which caused the death of 119 peoples in the Chittagong-Cox's Bazar coast (Hossain & Mullick, 2020; Wikipedia, 2023). Four more shorelines before and after the cyclone were developed using the four cloud-free Landsat 5 TM satellite images, Table 4 shows the details of the satellite images. The coastal plantation historical data and geo-location of the plantation were collected from the plantation journal of range offices of the Chittagong coastal division of Bangladesh Forest Division (BFD). After that, to get insight into the effect of the *Casuarina equisetifolia* (Jhau) plantation and the tropical cyclone on coastal retreat a pre-post plantation and a pre-post cyclone shoreline were developed and analysis through the DSAS.

Table 5: Details of satellite imagery used for the cyclone effect analysis.

Satellite/Sensor	Date	Cloud cover	Spatial resolution (m)
Landsat 5-TM	1997-02-20	0	30
Landsat 5-TM	1997-11-03	1	30
Landsat 5-TM	1990-10-31	0	30
Landsat 5-TM	1991-12-05	0	30

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Coastal profile across the beach at Sonadia Island

To create the beach profile, at first, a reconnaissance survey was conducted at the time of tracking the shoreline. After the reconnaissance survey, the Beach profile of Sonadia Island was taken at an approximate interval of 1.5-2 km based on convenience location. To get the approximate distance the study used SW Map tracking and Google Map distance measuring tools. Transect 1 was taken near the north point of Sonadia Island (Figure 18), in this transect there is only one noticeable dune with the *Casuarina equisetifolia* at the end of the transect. After the endpoint of the transect, there is the *Casuarina equisetifolia* forest with a gentle downward slope and then the canal that divides Sonadia Island from Maheshkhali. At this location, the Island spans approximately 150-200 meters along the shoreline. According to information obtained from key informants, specifically local fishers aged between 40 and 70 years, the island's width is diminishing over time, primarily on the west side facing the sea. Field surveys and analysis of historical satellite imagery revealed a consistent reduction in the island's width, accompanied by an expansion in the northern direction.

Figure 18: An illustrative beach profile of Transect 1 showing the relative elevation, slope, and location of sandy dunes and other components

Transect 2 was the second northern profile of Sonadia Island and has exclusive characteristics with Mangrove Vegetation (MV) at the end of the transect (Eastern side). This transect shows an upward slope up to 35m and then shows gently downward slope up to 70m and then a rapid downward with MV. Here, the transect has not only MV in a shorter distance but also the width of the island shortest. There are no recognizable dunes in this profile, only have MV after 70m which shows its existence up to the canal. According to the KII survey, the beach was rapidly moving from west to east and destroying the MV successively. During the time of field survey, the ruined lower trunk of MV trees was found at the drift line (Transect 2, Figure 19) and within the swash zone at the time of high tide. This destroyed lower trunk confirmed that there were mangrove trees a few years ago.

Figure 19: An illustrative beach profile of Transect 2 showing the relative elevation, slope, and location of sandy dunes and other components

However, during the field survey, we tried to identify the destruction process of MV, especially the suppressed pneumatophore and the basal part of the tree by the aeolian movement of sand and

gradual dying of the tree and then transferring the MV to the sandy beach. At the eastern part of this transect area, the newly died and presently dying trees were found and the process of suppressing the pneumatophore of MV and the sequential destroying process were identified (Transect 2, Figure 19b&c)

Transect 3 was the third beach profile starting from the northern point (Figure 20), one of the smallest beaches of Sonadia Island. In this transect there is a gentle upward slope up to 35m, after that, there is a single dune with *Vitex trifolia* and *Casuarina equisetifolia* (Jhau). After 40m the transect has almost plane land with *Casuarina equisetifolia* (Jhau) plantation forest. However, although the beach width was smaller than the previous two the island became somewhat wider in this section.

Figure 20: An illustrative beach profile of Transect 3&4 showing the relative elevation, slope, and location of sandy dunes and other components [Transect 3(a), Transect 4(b)]

Transect 4 shows comparatively flat in the first 40m of the transect (Figure 20), after that, a very shallow water channel was visible during the survey. Later from 60m to 140m the beach shows a gentle upward without any dunes, and then the *Casuarina equisetifolia* (Jhau) plantation with a flat ground was found during the survey.

Transect 5 was one of the diversified transects having many beach objects including the newly formed small dunes to a large stable dune with a *Casuarina equisetifolia* (Jhau) plantation (Figure

21). From the drift line to the first 30m it shows a gentle upward slope and then up to 60m it was somewhat flat. After that, from 60m to 90m, it was found a deep-water channel which had more than 1m depth and then, there was a gentle upward slope, and between 130-140m small and newly formed dunes with *Vitex trifolia* were found, around this dune more newly forming dunes were present. Near the ending point of the transect Between 150-180m, there was a dune with the highest peak (around 4m in comparison with the drift line). These were the highest dunes in parallel with the beach and after that within 50-100m the settlement of the west village (Paschim Para) of Sonadia Island was located. According to the local people, these dunes were larger in width and height before the cyclones of 1991 and 1997-98. During these two devastating cyclones, most of the largest dunes were destroyed and the small dunes were newly formed at that time.

Figure 21: An illustrative beach profile of Transect 5 showing the relative elevation, slope, location of sandy dunes, and other components

Transect 6 and transect 7 were taken between the beach area of Purba Para and Paschim Para of Sonadia Island (Figure 22). Transect 6 shows a gentle upward up to 35m then a bare dune, after

that other portion of this beach area shows somewhat flat. At the end of this transect, a gentle upward dune with a *Casuarina equisetifolia* (Jhau) plantation was present and inside the *Casuarina equisetifolia* (Jhau) plantation, most of the part was seen as flat land.

In the case of Transect 7, up to 120m of the beach, there are some small bare dunes and the rest of the part was flat. After 120m large and developed dunes with *Casuarina equisetifolia* (Jhau) plantation were present.

Figure 22: An illustrative beach profile of Transect 6&7 showing the relative elevation, slope, and location of sandy dunes and other components [Transect 6 (a), Transect 7 (b)]

Transect 8 was another diversified transect having more than one plant in a single developing dune (Figure 23). In this section of the beach, the number of dunes was also recognizable and in the highest number in the amount in comparison with all of the beach area of this Island. Only in this beach area, simultaneously *Vitex trifolia* and *Ipomoea pes-caprae* were found in the newly growing dunes. Before this transect starting from the north point, only *Vitex trifolia* was found on small dunes, and after this transect only *Ipomoea pes-caprae* were found in the developing dunes. In Transect 8 from the drift line toward the land the transect shows a gentle upward slope up to 40m, then shows several small to medium size growing dunes covered by *Vitex trifolia* and *Ipomoea pes-caprae*. Almost 150-200m on both side of this transect numerous this type of growing dunes was seen. At the ending side of this transect from 140-200m very wide development dunes were seen, which foreside (toward sea) were covered by *Vitex trifolia* and the hindside (toward land) was covered by *Casuarina equisetifolia* plantation. After 220m to forward many developed

dunes had higher elevation than the dunes located at 200m, with herbs and shrubs covered along with scattered *Casuarina equisetifolia* trees.

Figure 23: An illustrative beach profile of Transect 8 showing the relative elevation, slope, and location of sandy dunes and other components

Transect 9 is the second last transect taken by this study and is located near the southern point of Sonadia Island (Figure 24). This is the transect where dunes sliding was found during the survey, due to the wave of high tide the developed dunes having *Casuarina equisetifolia* (Jhau) plantation (Near this transect) and developing dunes (35m away from the drift line) were sliding and vanished into the beach and ocean. Here the dunes were *Ipomoea pes-caprae* dominated and had some sapling and early-stage growing *Casuarina equisetifolia*.

Transect 10 was located at the southern part of the beach of Sonadia Island and this transect was characterized by numerous growing dunes with *Ipomoea pes-caprae* (Figure 25). At this part of the beach, there are numerous small and medium-sized dunes with *Ipomoea pes-caprae* on both sides of the transect 500m at the northwestern side and 100m at the southeastern side. At the end

of this transect, there was a *Casuarina equisetifolia* (Jhau) plantation in flat land without any recognizable dunes.

Figure 24: An illustrative beach profile of Transect 9 showing the relative elevation, slope, and location of sandy dunes and other components.

Figure 25: An illustrative beach profile of Transect 10 showing the relative elevation, slope, and location of sandy dunes and other components

Figure 26: All coastal profile (Transect 1 to Transect 10) and their comparative slope, elevation, distance from drift line, and positions of other beach objects.

To put the initial point of all of the transects at the same elevation, the study considered an arbitrary benchmark (ABM) with an elevation of zero at the drift line position. After that, the reduced levels of all points along transects were calculated using ABM. Then, all of the transects were shown in a line chart to visualize the physio-morphological characteristics of the coast of the Sonadia island (Figure 26). Results show that the coastline of this beach was very diversified having very small (10-50cm) to very large (400-500cm) vertical dunes with or without vegetation cover. The elevation of the stable dunes at transects no. 5, 7, 8, and 9 shows the highest peak within the distance of 50-180m from the drift line. However, only the first 30-40m of the profile of all transect shows somewhat similarities as this part of the beach shows a gentle upward slope, after that the beach were very diversified in physio-morphological characteristics.

4.2 Shoreline change at Sonadia Island over the last half-century

The current study analyzes and visualizes the last half-century of coastal erosion and accretion dynamics at Sonadia Island using the DSAS tools and different statistical techniques including Shoreline Change Envelope (SCE), Net Shoreline Movement (NSM), Linear Regression Rate (LRR), Endpoint Rate (EPR), and Weighted LRR (WLR). After that, the study also analyzes the rate of erosion due to the sea level rise (SLR) by global warming, and the impact of vegetation cover on the coastal erosion process. Finally, a ten-year and twenty-year prediction of the shoreline position was visualized by using Kalman filter projection.

Table 6: Descriptive statistics of the different shoreline change parameters of Sonadia Island over the last 50 years (1972-2023).

Parameters	SCE	NSM	EPR	LRR	WLR
Minimum	6.33	-1172.37	-23.43	-24.12	-24.12
Maximum	1859.72	717.86	14.35	6.62	6.60
Mean	513.27	-42.89	-0.93	-1.90	-1.90
Standard Error	19.97	19.82	0.43	0.42	0.42
Count	297	297	297	281	281

The descriptive statistics (Table 6) of the whole shoreline change over the period based on around 300 transect data analysis showed that the maximum and minimum LRR are -24.12m/yr. and

6.62m/yr. respectively. Here the erosion mean value (-24.12m/yr.) is much higher in comparison with the accretion mean value (6.62m/yr.). The mean LRR and WLR for the period 1972-2023 were -1.9m/yr. and EPR was somewhat low -0.93m/yr. However, the standard error of the LRR, WLR, and EPR were respectively 0.42, 0.42, and 0.43.

4.2.1 Net Shoreline Movement

The result showed that the NSM at Sonadia Island was -42.89m on average based on the analysis of 297 transects indicating an overall erosion at this Island between the 1972 to 2023 period. The total number of transects with negative NSM was 132 (44.44%), where the maximum negative NSM was 1172.37m at transect 226 (Figure 27) and the average negative value was 335.78m. On the other hand, although the number of the transect 165 (55.56%) was higher in number with positive NSM indicating accretion the average value was 191.42m, and the maximum value was 717.86m at transect 233 (Figure 27), both of these were less in comparison with erosion value. By analyzing the NSM measurement, it was clear that this Island is prone to erosion, and the most dynamic part where both the erosion and accretion were higher amount is the southern site starting from the Paschim Para until the south point. Analysis of NSM shows between these 50 years the middle part in front of the Purba Para and the northern show a comparatively accretion nature with somewhat exceptions (Figure 27).

Figure 27: Net shoreline movement indicating the distance between the shoreline of 1972 and 2023 at Sonadia Island.

4.2.2 Shoreline Change Envelope

Shoreline change envelope (SCE) indicates the maximum change value at each transect among all shorelines which is erosion and accretion independent, based on the calculation of 297 transects, it was found that the average value of SCE is 513.27m, with maximum distance as 1859.72m at transect 227 and the minimum distance as 6.33m at transect 21. Based on the SCE finding it was clear that from the north point to the Paschim para (Transect 11 to Transect 211) there has been less shoreline erosion and succession trend in the last half-century. Whereas, the southern part had a greater trend of erosion and accretion (Figure 28).

Figure 28: Shoreline change envelope indicating the distance between the two most distant shorelines along the transect.

Both the values of NSM and SCE indicate that the southern part of this Island is very vulnerable to accretion and erosion. On the other hand, the middle part shows somewhat stable (Figure 29), and overall net gain was shown in this region. Whereas, the northern site shows mostly accretion scenario and the accretion is continuously going on in this part (Figure 29). Due to the new accretion in the shoreline in 2023 and not having another shoreline the most northern first 10 transects couldn't calculate the NSM and SCE value in this transect (Figure 29).

Figure 29: Net shoreline movement and Shoreline change envelope at transect 11 to transect 307.

4.2.3 End Point Rate

The Endpoint rate (EPR) as a meter per year derived from the NSM value showed that the average rate is -0.93m/yr. with an uncertainty of $\pm 0.37\text{m/yr.}$ based on the analysis of 297 transects. From 132 (44.44%) of erosional transect 43.43% was found as statistically significant erosion. The average erosion rate was 7.46m/yr. with the maximum rate at transect no. 226 as 23.43m/yr. In the case of accretion rate, EPR analysis showed that 165 (55.56%) transect shows accretion, where 50.51% have been found as statistically significant. Transect 233, showed the maximum value of accretion rate as 14.35m/yr. , where the average accretion rate was 4.31m/yr. (Figure 30).

Figure 30: Shoreline erosion and accretion rate based on EPR, LRR, and WLR at different transects along the coastline of Sonadia Island.

4.2.4 Linear regression rate

The LRR is the slope of the regression line representing the intersecting points of all shorelines and their distance from the baseline (Himmelstoss et al., 2021). A linear regression method uses a linear equation to get the best-fit model of the rate of change with time (Das et al., 2021; Kuleli et al., 2011; Zambrano-Medina et al., 2023). The positive value of slope indicates the accretion of the coast line and the negative value of slope indicates the erosion of the coastline, the higher the slope the greater the rate of change. LRR is very suitable for the longer period change analysis of the coastline change (Zambrano-Medina et al., 2023) and it is also free from the outlier effect (Himmelstoss et al., 2021).

Based on the LRR of a total of 281 transects the average rate was found as -1.9m/yr. with an uncertainty of $\pm 4.28\text{m/yr}$. The uncertainty of LRR was found as higher in comparison with the

EPR (Figure 30). The number of erosional transects was found as 138 (49.11%) with a maximum erosion rate of 24.12m/yr. at the transect no. 226 (Figure 31), whereas the average rate was found as -7.14m/yr. In the case of accretion, the average rate was found as 3.15m/yr. among the 143 (50.89%) of the transects and the maximum rate was found as 6.62m/yr. at the transect no. 185.

Figure 31: Linear regression rate at different transects; transect no. 185 (below left) has the highest accretion rate, transect no. 226 (below right) has the highest erosion rate, and transect no. 264 (Above right) has an average rate.

4.2.5 Weighted linear regression rate

Through the analysis of a total of 281 transects, the WLR rate was shown as an average rate - 1.9m/yr. with a similar rate of LRR with an uncertainty of ± 4.25 m/yr. (Figure 30). The number of erosional transects was found as 138 (49.11%) with a maximum erosion rate of 24.12m/yr. at the transect no. 226, whereas the average rate was found as -7.12m/yr. In the case of accretion, the average rate was found as 3.11m/yr. among the 143 (50.89%) of the transects and the maximum rate was found as 6.60m/yr. at the transect no. 185. The study found an almost similar value with both LRR and WLR analysis, this is also shown in the correlation analysis (Figure 32).

4.3 Correlation between different statistical analyses

A correlation study was used to check the agreement of the results between different statistics (Figure 32). A high level to very high level of agreement was found between the different statistical rates used during the analysis. A higher level of positive correlation was shown between EPR vs LRR ($R^2 = 0.78$), EPR vs WLR ($R^2 = 0.70$), and a very high level of positive correlation was shown between LRR vs WLR ($R^2 = 0.94$) indicating that there has a general trend of change at the study area.

Figure 32: Correlation between different statistical change rates (EPR, LRR, and WLR) used for the study.

4.4 Trend analysis of coastal erosion and accretion

The study analyzes a trend by dividing the whole period into three sub-periods, *VIZ.* 1972-1989, 1989-1999, and 1999-2023 (Table 7). Results show that the Island had a higher level of erosion rate (LRR= -6.23m/yr.) in the period 1972-1989. In the period 1989-1999, the erosion reduced to a great extent and accretion started at a rate of a similar extent (LRR = 6.06m/yr.).

However, this rate again decreases in the period 1999-2023, but the accretion process still going on at a rate of 1.15m/yr. (LRR). From the accretion and erosion average trend (Figure 33a) it was

found that both the erosion and accretion rate increased in the period 1989-1999, this may be the result of the two devastating cyclone effects in the study area by 1991 and 1997. The LRR result of all transects shows that most of the accretion transects were located on the northern and middle sides of the Island, whereas most of the eroded transects were located in the southern part of the

Figure 33: Trend of linear regression rate from 1972 to 2023: a) Overall mean LRR, mean erosion and accretion rate trend line; b) LRR for all transect.

Island (Figure 33b). That means the Island shows overall erosion in the southern part and overall accretion in the northern and middle parts. The trend of LRR and EPR also shows a similar trend of erosion and accretion on this Island (Figure 34).

Figure 34: The result of the shoreline change (erosion and accretion) estimated from Endpoint rate (EPR) and Linear regression rate (LRR); a) Change between 1972 to 1989, b) Change between 1989 to 1999, and c) Change between 1999 to 2023.

4.5 Effect of SLR on Coastal Erosion

The current study used an average rate of 5mm/yr. and 7.8mm/yr. per year at the highest rate on the eastern coast of Bangladesh (Singh, 2002; Uzzaman, 2014) to calculate coastal erosion due to SLR. The slope of the active near shore of Sonadia Island was calculated based on the average slope of ten nearshore profiles (Equation x) taken by a dumpy level survey on 24-28 August 2023. Figure 35 shows the location of the transect where the coastal profiles were taken. The slope of each profile was measured based on the horizontal distance (d) and the vertical shift (h) between the point at the drift line point and the point out of nearshore, where the profile shows almost flat and free from coastal regular changes and other phenomenon. After that using the equation

(Equation x) the value of the slope of the coastal profile $\tan(\beta)$ was found as 0.019. Different studies on the global and regional distribution of the nearshore slope found that the slope of the nearshore varies from place to place, for example, a global estimation found the upper and lower limits of the nearshore slope as 0.2 and 0.001 (Athanasidou et al., 2019). Some other regional studies also found the nearshore mean observed slope within this range, like; the Dutch coast as 0.0083, the North Californian coast as 0.0156, the South Californian coast as 0.0204, the New Jersey coast as 0.01, and the Emilia Romagna coast as 0.0062 etc. (Athanasidou et al., 2019). By using the Bruun rule (Bruun, 1962), the study found that SLR from 5mm to 7.8mm per year causes coastal erosion at a rate of 0.263m/yr. to 0.41m/yr., which is 13.77% to 21.58% of the total erosion rate considering LRR -1.9m/yr. and 28.28% to 40.09% considering EPR -0.93m/yr. over the last 50 years.

Table 7: Descriptive statistics of the shoreline change trend at Sonadia Island

Parameters	LRR 1972-1989	LRR 1989-1999	LRR 1999-1923
Mean	-6.23	6.09	1.15
Standard Error	1.22	1.91	0.77
Median	-6.29	4.63	2.61
Minimum	-64.7	-91.9	-38.74
Maximum	64.11	80.03	25.54
Number of transects	234	233	250

Figure 35: Location of the ten coastal profiles used for measuring the nearshore mean slope at Sonadia Island.

4.6 Effect of Tropical Cyclone on coastal erosion

The effect of the two devastating cyclones (April 29, 1991, and Cyclone 19 May 1997) over the last 50 years (Hossain & Mullick, 2020; Wikipedia, 2023), which has had the greatest impact on this landscape and life in this region were considered to analyze the effect of the cyclone on coastal erosion. For this purpose, the NSM (meter) and EPR (meter/year) were used for the analysis of the coastal erosion and accretion trend at the coastal belt of Sonadia over the last 50 years. The NSM and EPR were selected because, to calculate LRR and WLR, a long-term trend in change rate is required (Himmelstoss et al., 2021) and the year 1991 and 1997 has only two shorelines as well as the time interval between this shoreline are very small to calculate LRR or WLR. The development of more shorelines was also not possible due to the unavailability of cloud-free satellite images during this period in the study area. To calculate NSM and EPR in 1991, a total of 215 transects were cast along the beach with an interval of 50. The result shows that 70.23% of the transect shows erosion and 29.77% shows accretion (Figure 36). In this year, the maximum erosion and

accretion were found in transect no. 231 and transect no. 201 respectively -251.03m and 901.51m, both of the transects located in the southern part of the island after the Paschim para. In 1997, a total of 226 transects were cast and the finding shows that 77.88% of transect shows erosion and 22.12% shows accretion (Figure 36). In this year, the maximum erosion and accretion were found in transect no. 12 and transect no. 229 respectively as -98.26m and 192.79m, here the maximum eroded transect is located in the northern part, and the accretion point is in the southern part of the island.

Results of the analysis over the last 50 years showed that the Island had a moderate level of erosion over the period 1972-1989, at this time the EPR was -6.37m/yr. and this rate reduced greatly after this period and an accretion trend of EPR 0.46m/yr. at the period 1989-1999 was shown. However, this accretion trend converted into a high level of erosion during the year of the cyclone in 1991 at -10.59m/yr. and in 1997 as -20.7m/yr., although the cyclone in 1991 was highly devastating in comparison with 1997, the EPR shows the value was almost two times in 1997 than the rate in 1991 (Figure 36). The following two may be the possible reasons behind this phenomenon; a) the devastating cyclone in 1991 made the island more vulnerable which influenced the erosion rate in 1997, b) in 1997 the time interval of the two shorelines was around 9 months, where the interval in 1991 was around 1 year and 2 months. Due to an accretion trend over this period (1989-1999), after the cyclone, there may have been a higher level of accretion which caused the reduction in the overall EPR in 1991. However, again the island is back to its accretion trend from 1999-2023 with an accretion rate of 2.48m/yr.

Figure 36: The impact of the two devastating tropical cyclones in 1991 and 1997 accelerated the coastal erosion rate at Sonadia Island.

4.7 Predicting future shoreline in 2033 and 2043

By using the Kalman Filter (Kalman, 1960), which is a default tool in the DSAS 5.1 Add-in at ArcGIS 10.8 interface, the study found that most of the accretion will happen in the northern to the middle part of the Island without some exception. Some portions of the middle part located in front of Purba para starting from Transect No. 112 to Transect No. 150 have at risk of a higher level of erosion around 50-200m by 2034 and 50-250m by 2044 (Figure 37). However, most of the southern part will remain at risk of erosion by 2034 and 2044 but Transect No. 219 to 224 have a greater risk of erosion in comparison with the other transects (Figure 38). These specific transects have a chance of erosion from 200-300m erosion by 2034 and 300-550m by 2044 (Figure 37).

Figure 37: Present shoreline (2023) and projected shoreline (2034 and 2044) position relating to baseline.

Some exception in the southern part was noticed at Transect No. 240 to 255 where there is a chance of accretion from the range of 20-350m by the end of 2034, and Transect No. 242 to 258 have a chance of accretion by the end of 2044 at a range of 30-330m (Figure 37). The rest of the part of the south point shows erosion possibilities in the upcoming future (Figure 38).

4.8 Effect of Coastal Plantation on Erosion

Based on the analysis of 149 transects with 50m intervals along the beach starting from the northern side to the southern side of the Island, the plantation was visible from 2006 to the following year as a result of a successful plantation starting from 2003 and ending in 2015. Before and after this period there have not been any plantation activities on this Island (Sonadia beat) according to the Range officer of Gorokghata range of Cox's Bazar coastal forest division. The study excludes the most northern and southern parts for the analysis of the impact of vegetation on coastal erosion as this site there have not any visible established plantations from satellite images (Google Earth Pro high-resolution image) in the years 2007, 2010, and 2013, after that a very small amount of vegetation coverage was seen at the southern part from 2015 to onward.

Figure 38: Shoreline profile along the beach with 10 years (2034) and 20 years (2044) projection and uncertainty.

Based on the historical erosion and accretion result at the part of the beach, where the plantation gets established well the study reveals that the site shows an overall mean erosion rate of -0.321m/yr. (EPR) to -0.50m/yr. (LRR) at the period 1972 to 1999 (Table 8). However, after the establishment of the plantation (2005 -2023), the area shows a mean rate of accretion of 8.70m/yr. both the EPR and LRR (Table 8). Results also show that the minimum erosion rate both for the EPR and LRR reduces after the plantation establishment and the maximum accretion rate also increases (Table 8) by the plantation establishment. Based on the current analysis the study found that plantation has a great impact on the erosion and accretion of the coastal belt of Sonadia.

Table 8: Erosion and accretion status before plantation (1972-1999) establishment and after plantation (2005-2023) establishment.

Parameters	EPR	LRR	EPR	LRR
	1972-1999	1972-1999	2005-2023	2005-2023
Mean	-0.32	-0.50	8.70	8.70
Minimum	-9.2	-9.42	-7.82	-7.81
Maximum	15.41	15.59	19.98	19.97
Standard Error	0.45	0.46	0.68	0.68
Median	-1.28	-1.38	10.32	10.3
Total transect	149	149	149	149

However, to assess the influence of the width of the vegetation belt on coastal erosion and accretion, the study utilized very high-resolution satellite imagery from 2023, provided by Esri through the ArcGIS interface as a base map, to digitize the coastal vegetation belt width along the shoreline of Sonadia.

Figure 39: Effect of *Casuarina equisetifolia* (Jhau) plantation belt width on the shoreline erosion and accretion at Sonadia Island.

Among the 307 transects, 214 of them revealed the presence of coastal plantations with *Casuarina equisetifolia* (Jhau) vegetation. The DSAS tools were employed to assess both the accretion and erosion patterns of these 214 transects between 2013 to 2023, as well as to measure the width of their coastal vegetation in 2023. Subsequently, a regression analysis was performed utilizing

Python 3 data analysis modules within the Jupyter Notebook environment to examine the correlation between coastal erosion and accretion and the width of the vegetation, as determined post-2013. The findings indicate that the width of the vegetation belt has a statistically significant effect at a 95% confidence level ($P < 0.05$) on reducing coastal erosion, while it does not have any statistically significant impact on coastal accretion (Figure 39).

4.9 Effect of sandy dunes on coastal erosion and accretion

To analyze the influence of coastal sandy dunes and dunes maximum elevation (Table 9) on the shoreline erosion and accretion the study conducted a regression analysis between the number of dunes per transects and NSM, maximum elevation of dunes and NSM (Figure 40). The results demonstrate a statistically significant relationship at a 95% confidence level ($P < 0.05$) between the number of dunes per transect and NSM. Figure 40a illustrates that an increase in the number of dunes at a transect leads to a significant decrease in erosion and an increase in accretion along the shoreline. Among the 10 transects studied, the most significant shoreline erosion was observed at transect 2, measuring -110.21 meters, where only one dune (Figure 19) existed without any vegetation cover. Conversely, the maximum accretion was observed at transect 7, measuring 312.05 meters, which had three dunes (Figure 22), with two being bare and one having the coverage of an established *Casuarina equisetifolia* (Jhau) plantation.

Table 9: Number of dunes and dunes maximum elevation as well as vegetation belt width for all transect at Sonadia Island.

Transect	Vegetation width (m)	NSM (m)	Number of Dunes	Dunes maximum elevation
Transect 1	19.45	42.12	1	2.65
Transect 2	0.00	-110.21	1	1.48
Transect 3	269.12	-116.85	1	2.40
Transect 4	152.78	79.63	1	1.93
Transect 5	0.00	145.61	2	4.19
Transect 6	388.57	-77.64	2	2.40
Transect 7	341.28	312.04	3	4.16
Transect 8	214.14	220.27	3	4.48
Transect 9	21.78	0.00	1	3.90

Transect	Vegetation width (m)	NSM (m)	Number of Dunes	Dunes maximum elevation
Transect 10	123.74	135.83	3	1.95

When examining the correlation between the maximum elevation of dunes and shoreline erosion and accretion, the findings indicate that as the elevation of existing dunes increases, shoreline erosion is significantly reduced ($P < 0.05$), as illustrated in Figure 40b. Among the 10 transects studied, specifically Transects 2, 3, and 6, exhibited erosion (Table 9), and each of these transects featured dunes with maximum elevations of less than 2.5 meters.

Figure 40: Impact of sandy dunes and their elevation on the coastal erosion-accretion and relations of dunes and their elevation with the coastal vegetation width

Conversely, the highest accretion levels were observed at Transects 7 and 8, where the maximum elevation of the dunes reached 4.16 meters and 4.48 meters, respectively, as detailed in Table 9.

The research also performed a regression analysis to examine the connection between the number of sandy dunes, their maximum elevation, and the width of the vegetation belt along the transects. The findings indicate that there is no statistically significant correlation between the variables tested and the width of the vegetation belt (Figure 40c&d).

4.10 The natural formation of the sandy dunes at Sonadia Island

Macrophyte wrack comprises seaweeds, driftwood, grasses, and other organic matters in the beach environment that wash ashore and stay in the drift line of the beach area promoting the dunes formation process in the very early stage (Anonymous, 2023; Marshall & Banks, 2013). Wrack plays an important role in the beach ecosystem in two ways: a) provide support in the food wave of marine and terrestrial ecosystem and incorporate the herbivores, and b) provide nutrient to the coastal ecosystem by decomposing and habitat support for the macrofauna (Marshall & Banks, 2013). Dunes form when winds blow the sand particles and make a mound behind an obstacle, the common obstacle in the beach area is the wrack (Anonymous, 2023).

In Sonadia Island the dunes formation begins with the emergence of the *Ipomoea pes-caprae* pioneer grasses (Figure 41) by absorbing the nutrients provided by the decomposition of the macrophyte wrack (Figure 42). The higher-elevation dunes are gradually formed by the trapping of the sand by the pioneer vegetation (Marshall & Banks, 2013). At Sonadia, the pioneer herb *Ipomoea pes-caprae* traps the sand particles at the time of aeolian movement and gradually increases the height of the dunes behind the *Ipomoea pes-caprae* (Figure 43a&b). In the secondary stage, the vertical elevation of the dunes gradually increases through the continuous sand-trapping process of *Ipomoea pes-caprae* and *Vitex trifolia*. However, in the very early stage, the trapping of sand occurred by *Ipomoea pes-caprae* only, and in the middle stage, the *Ipomoea pes-caprae* and the *Vitex trifolia* combined, after the *Vitex trifolia* domination appeared in the dunes (Figure 43c) and other climax species appeared gradually.

In the course of the field survey, it was observed that the southern extremity of the island extends southward, while the northern extremity extends northward, resulting in a tapering configuration at the peak of both ends.

Figure 41: Two dominant species in the dunes of Sonadia island, *Vitex trifolia* (Vitex) and *Ipomoea pes-caprae* (Ipomoea).

Figure 42: Macrophyte wrack at the beach of Sonadia Island; a & b) seaweeds, driftwoods, and grasses, c) decomposing wrack and providing nutrient support.

Figure 43: Developing sandy dunes through trapping the aeolian moving sand by vegetation; a&b) formation of dunes by *Ipomoea pes-caprae*, c&d) further development of the newly formed dunes by both the *Ipomoea pes-caprae* and *Vitex trifolia*.

4.11 Degradation process of the developed dunes

Sometimes the strong winds generate waves that may flatten the dune's peak and may also produce very steep peaks on the beach berm that drive the dunes to be eroded (Marshall & Banks, 2013). Back sweep by large waves is one of the major causes of the erosion of the foredunes in coastal areas (Botero et al., 2017; Portz, 2008). The strong back sweep creates an overall negative sediment budget in the beach profile and makes the natural reconstruction process of dunes difficult (Botero et al., 2017). Field survey result and the informal interview with the local fishers reveals that the major cause of the degradation of the dunes and shoreline is the strong wave hit by the ocean (Figure 44 a, b&c). As per information provided by indigenous fishers and elderly participants, the dunes on the island exhibited greater height and dimensions prior to the cyclones of 1991 and 1997. These cyclones, characterized by their destructive nature, significantly eroded the majority of the island's dunes. Presently, the observable dunes largely comprise newly formed

Figure 44: Degradation process of sandy dunes at Sonadia island; a, b, & c) degradation of dunes by the coastal wave hit, d) further degradation of the partially degraded dunes by cattle grazing, e & f) Severe erosion uncovered the underground mudstone layer at the south point of the Island.

structures following the cyclonic events. It is noteworthy that this region experiences frequent tropical cyclones annually, owing to its geographical location. In some cases, cattle grazing in partially degraded dunes accelerates the degradation process (Figure 44d). At the time of the field survey some places were found as dunes slid by the strong wave hit although the dunes have recognizable height and vegetation coverage as well as *Casuarina equisetifolia* (Jhau) plantation (Figures 44a, b&c). Figure 44 e&f shows the extremely degraded shoreline in the southern side of the Sonadia by the hit of coastal wave.

In the present investigation, our observations indicate a noteworthy reduction in shoreline erosion when dunes exceed a height of 4.0 meters from the drift line (Figure 40 & Table 9). Additionally, our findings reveal a significant decrease in shoreline erosion with the widening of coastal vegetation (Figure 40 & Figure 39). However, in the context of shoreline accretion, the width of the vegetation strip does not exert a significant influence (Figure 39). Furthermore, our analysis demonstrates that the width of the vegetation strip does not significantly impact the elevation and number of dunes (Figure 40). During the field investigation, it was observed that a significant portion of the Jhau plantation areas lacks substantial underground vegetation. As explained by the coastal Divisional Forest Officer, Mr. Abdur Rahman, the dunes beneath the Jhau plantation undergo widening and flattening subsequent to the establishment of the plantation. This phenomenon is attributed to the plantation's utilization of a 2m x 2m spacing, resulting in the rapid formation of a dense canopy shortly after plantation, thereby detrimentally impacting the underground vegetation.

4.12 Potential restoration measures of partially degraded dunes

Dunes are very dynamic by nature, and the sand of the dunes regularly moves in response to local winds, waves, and storms. Preventing the erosion of the dunes is much easier than the restoration of the dunes (Superior Groundcover, 2021). By analyzing the literature, it was found that the dune erosion controls by native vegetation, beach nourishment, and dunes forming fences are the widely used dune restoration techniques (Anonymous, 2023; Botero et al., 2017; Kidd, 2001; Marshall & Banks, 2013).

To hold the sand on the beaches the most cost-effective way is to protect the natural habitat and physical environment of the beach (Marshall & Banks, 2013). Maintaining a protective cover with suitable native vegetation may control wind erosion (Kidd, 2001) and nourishment of the beach is

another environmentally friendly technique to control beach erosion by reducing the wave energy with an expanded and wider beach which may be used for tourism purposes (Botero et al., 2017). Dunes forming fences also works by reducing wind velocity and depositing them in the nearby fence and this is useful where beach nourishment and earthmoving are quite not convenient (Kidd, 2001). However, before taking steps on the beach nourishment or erosion control measures or dunes restoration measures care should be taken about choosing the best environmentally suitable steps for the beach, as a poor restoration measure may cause a negative impact and accelerate the further erosion (Superior Groundcover, 2021).

Based on the results obtained from our current investigation, we propose the implementation of the following measures to effectively restore the degraded dunes and eroded shoreline of Sonadia Island: a) Increasing the width of the coastal vegetation strip is recommended, as our findings indicate a significant reduction in shoreline erosion with an increased strip width of the coastal plantation. However, our current study did not differentiate the impact of *Casuarina equisetifolia* (Jhau) or coastal mangroves on shoreline erosion and accretion. Further research is necessary to determine the suitability of species for erosion control; b) Artificially enriching the height of dunes may contribute to the reduction of shoreline erosion. Our study reveals that dunes with a height exceeding 4 meters significantly mitigate shoreline erosion; c) Increasing the number of dunes through the artificial placement of sand or macrophyte wrack to create new dunes can be employed to diminish shoreline erosion. The increment in the number of dunes correlates with a substantial reduction in coastal erosion; d) Implementing measures to control cattle grazing in partially degraded dunes is advised to prevent further degradation and promote the eventual restoration of the dunes; e) Although our current study did not investigate the control access for coastal erosion reduction, it is considered a potentially suitable strategy for Sonadia. Existing scientific literature generally supports its positive impact on coastal conservation.

CHAPTER FIVE

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

The current study utilizes the comprehensive analysis of coastal dynamics at Sonadia Island, using the satellite imageries of Landsat series, dumpy level survey, GPS surveys, Key Informant Interview (KII) survey, sea level rise (SLR) information, coastal profile information, coastal plantation information with geolocation, and the coastal vegetation strip width generated from the google earth pro and ArcGIS base map of very high-resolution satellite data having 15cm to 2.5m spatial resolution. Results reveal a complex interplay of natural and anthropogenic factors that have significantly impacted this dynamic coastal ecosystem over the past 50 years.

In the case of historical erosion and accretion patterns, the study found a noteworthy shift in erosion and accretion patterns over the years. While devastating cyclones in 1991 and 1997 accelerated erosion, plantation activities between 2003 and 2015 have led to substantial accretion in previously eroding areas. The Island exhibited an overall erosion rate ranging from 0.93 meters per year (EPR) to 1.9 meters per year (LRR) between 1972 and 2023. This highlights the dynamic nature of coastal landscapes and underscores the potential for mitigation strategies through afforestation and ecosystem restoration.

After that, the research underscores the alarming impact of sea level rise (SLR) on Sonadia Island. SLR alone has contributed to a significant percentage of erosion over the last five decades. The SLR was responsible for approximately 13.77-21.58% of the erosion when taking LRR into account, and it contributed to approximately 28.28-40.09% of the erosion when considering EPR on Sonadia Island during the last five decades emphasizing the urgent need for climate change adaptation measures in coastal regions.

In predictive modeling using Kalman Filter provides a valuable tool for forecasting future shoreline positions. The finding of the predictive model indicates that future shoreline positions in 2034 and 2044 will likely experience accretion predominantly in the northern and middle sections, while the southern region remains at risk of erosion.

The current study utilized secondary data obtained from the Range officer of Gorokghata range in the Cox's Bazar coastal forest division, focused on the coastal plantation at Sonadia Island. The findings indicate a noteworthy decrease in erosion attributed to the presence of coastal plantations. Another aspect of the study involved an examination of 214 transects with coastal vegetation, revealing a substantial reduction in coastal erosion with an increase in vegetation width. Furthermore, an analysis of the coastal profile based on 10 transects at Sonadia indicated that the width of coastal vegetation did not have a significant effect on the number and elevation of dunes. However, the study identified that the number and elevation of dunes exerted a significant influence on the reduction of coastal erosion.

In the end, the study analyzed the sandy dune's natural formation, historical degradation, and potential restoration measures based on the KII survey, field observation, and intensive literature review. Results reveal that the macrophyte wrack and the pioneer herbs *Ipomoea pes-caprae* play major roles in the early stage of the dune formation. At the middle stage the *Vitex trifolia* shrubs, locally known as Nishinda get dominated in the dunes. Later the climax species appeared gradually. The major causes of dune degradation were found as the strong waves by the ocean and the cattle grazing in the degraded dunes.

Finally, the findings of the current research have critical implications for coastal management and conservation efforts. These statistical results provide a robust foundation for evidence-based coastal management. Policymakers, environmentalists, and local communities can use these findings to implement targeted strategies for conservation and restoration, ensuring the long-term resilience and preservation of this vital coastal ecosystem of Sonadia Island.

5.2 Recommendations

Based on the final findings the current study recommends the following measures to make the Island sustainable and reduce the impact of climate change, SLR, flood, and anthropogenic actors on coastal erosion:

1. The study encourages and supports the restoration of coastal vegetation, as observed in the study between 2003 and 2015, which contributed to accretion in eroding areas. This can be achieved through afforestation and conservation efforts, but the afforestation with the native vegetation is highly recommended by many researchers (Anonymous, 2023; Botero et al., 2017; Kidd, 2001; Marshall & Banks, 2013).

2. Increasing the width of the coastal vegetation strip is recommended, as our findings indicate a significant reduction in shoreline erosion with an increased strip width of the coastal plantation.
3. Artificially enriching the height of dunes may contribute to the reduction of shoreline erosion. The study reveals that dunes with a higher elevation significantly mitigate shoreline erosion.
4. Increasing the number of dunes through the artificial placement of sand or macrophyte wrack to create new dunes can be employed to diminish shoreline erosion. Since the increase in the number of dunes correlates with a substantial reduction in coastal erosion.
5. Implementing measures to control cattle grazing, and control access is recommended to prevent further degradation of partially degraded dunes and promote the ultimate restoration of the dunes.
6. Establishing a continuous and comprehensive coastal monitoring program using satellite imagery and GIS tools to assess changes in coastal dynamics is recommended. Regular survey and monitoring are necessary to get the in-depth dynamics of the sandy dunes as it changes their physio-morphological features throughout the years.
7. Utilizing the predictive models, like the Kalman Filter mentioned in the study, to forecast future shoreline changes may be helpful for planning infrastructure and development projects in a way that minimizes vulnerability to erosion and loss of infrastructures.

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Annexes

Annex 1: Photo gallery of field survey at Sonadia Island

<p>Waiting for the Boat at Gorokghata</p>	<p>Set up of Leveling Staff</p>
<p>On the way to Sonadia by Local Boat</p>	<p>Set up of Dumpy Level</p>
<p>Reached at Sonadia Purba Para</p>	<p>Taking Staff reading</p>

Annex 2: Field book and reduced level (RL) calculation of Dumpy level survey; This is the calculation of RL for Transect 7 taking the arbitrary benchmark (BM) of 2 meters (Here, HI is the Height of Instrument and LC is the landcover).

Station	distance	Lat	Long	BR	IR	FR	LC	HI	RL	BM
A	0	21.88624	91.87976	2.04			B	4.04	2	2
	10				1.6				2.44	
	20				1.45				2.59	
	30				1.24				2.8	
	40				1.21				2.83	
	50				1.13				2.91	
	60				1.18				2.86	
	70				1.33				2.71	
	80				1.41				2.63	
	90				1.08				2.96	
	95				1.11				2.93	
	98				0.88				3.16	
B	101			0.2		0.18	D	4.06	3.86	
	104				0.93				3.13	
	110				1.17				2.89	
	120				1				3.06	
	125				0.54		D		3.52	
C	130			3.21		1.23		6.04	2.83	
	135				0.24		J		5.8	
	140				0.12		D		6.16	
	150				0.54				5.5	
	160	21.48716	91.88071		0.4	0.4			5.64	

Annex 3: Calculation of the average nearshore slope at Sonadia Island based on the coastal profile of the Dumpy level survey.

Transect	Distance	Elevation	Slope (B)	Slope value
T1	115	2.24	tanB1	0.0195
T2	100	0.63	tanB2	0.0063
T3	60	2.17	tanB3	0.0362
T4	165	1.93	tanB4	0.0117
T5	180	1.05	tanB5	0.0058
T6	86	2.27	tanB6	0.0264
T7	160	3.64	tanB7	0.0228
T8	220	4.31	tanB8	0.0196
T9	70	3.41	tanB9	0.0487
T10	150	0.4	tanB10	0.0027
			Average Slope	0.1996

Annex 4: Descriptive statistics of the different parameters of shoreline change used during DSAS analysis from 1972 to 2023 at Sonadia Island.

Parameters	SCE	NSM	EPR	LRR	WLR
Mean	513.27	-42.89	-0.93	-1.90	-1.90
Standard Error	19.97	19.82	0.43	0.42	0.42
Median	412.98	21.21	0.50	0.24	0.24
Mode	330.72	0.00	0.00	-11.54	-11.54
Standard Deviation	344.15	341.58	7.38	7.01	7.01
Sample Variance	118437.49	116675.28	54.53	49.17	49.17
Kurtosis	2.98	1.02	0.29	1.04	1.04
Skewness	1.49	-1.02	-0.84	-1.27	-1.27
Range	1853.39	1890.23	37.78	30.74	30.74
Minimum	6.33	-1172.37	-23.43	-24.12	-24.12
Maximum	1859.72	717.86	14.35	6.62	6.62
Sum	152442.14	-12738.45	-274.80	-535.05	-535.05
Total transects	297	297	297	281	281
Confidence Level (95.0%)	39.30	39.01	0.84	0.82	0.82